

PRESS AND PUBLIC SPEECH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8031470>

Abstract: Titles have been the subject of much analysis in various fields. They arouse the interest of the students. They use specific language strategies in different areas: rhetoric, linguistics, social discourse, pragmatics, etc. In the following article, we will talk about some interesting studies that focus on these areas.

Key words: press, speech, discourse, title, text, linguistics, pragmatics.

It should be noted that in the present conditions, where the process of social renewal is being observed, mass media, including newspaper texts, are undergoing evolutionary changes. The press, which is rapidly developing, is considered as a torch that illuminates the general situation in the world, small and various events in daily life, relations and processes related to personal and social interest with necessary sources and foundations.

Indeed, in today's world of culture, a newspaper is a newspaper the discursive presentation of the information in the titles and the understanding of its content are of great importance. Nowadays, social life with countless networks is unthinkable without newspapers.

We know that "Press" refers to printed forms of mass media ¹. The press includes newspapers, magazines, almanacs. "The press is a set of all printed products, in the narrow sense, it represents periodicals, mainly newspapers and magazines (synonym - press), as a sharp and effective tool of social consciousness, it has a constant and active influence on the society of individuals, forms public opinion, is considered a powerful ideological factor in instilling certain views into the public mind, and illuminates the life of society in various (social-political, economic-production, scientific-technical) directions ². " Expressive expressions, figurative means, precedent events are actively used, especially in everyday life, to have a great pragmatic effect, and all these events are certainly studied by press linguistics.

Titles have been the subject of much analysis in various fields. They arouse the interest of students. They use specific language strategies in different areas: rhetoric, linguistics, social discourse, pragmatics, etc. Here are some interesting studies focusing on these areas:

In literature and literary criticism, the works of J. Ricardo, K. Grivel, G. Jenetta, R. Barth, K. Monsele, K. Ducchet, L. Hook, O. Ducro and JM Schaeffer are known.

In press and social discourse we find studies by J. Peytard, P. Charaudeau, F. Frandsen, C. Furet, P. Goldenstein, F. Sullet-Nylander.

linguistics, J. Ray-Debove studied the autonomy of certain language units, such as the title.

In the field of painting, B. Bosredon wrote his thesis on the title of the painting.

¹ Gurevich, S.M. Reportage v gazette / S.M. Gurevich // Problemy informatsii v gazete. M., 1971. - S. 87-99.

² <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Press>

In the field of literature and literary criticism, the title is mainly the lover of the literary work. For example, G. Genette calls the title a "paratext", which states that the "paratext" is at the beginning of the work of art that forms part of the thing.

J. Ricardo studied the titles of novels from a rhetorical point of view. "The title takes precedence over the book cover as the door that opens to the reader because "the cover is the protected screen through which the title unfolds. The title, which plays the role of the first page, causes the reader to go through the single entry point of the text to the single exit path," says the scientist.

K. Grivel (1973) examines the semantics of novel names in his "Production de l'intérêt romanesque". K. Grivel states: "the power of the title lies in the fact that the text is read and experienced."

For C. Duchet (1977), the title is a chain of literary work and social discourse. "To interrogate the novel in its name is also to reach one of its social dimensions, since the name arises from the meeting of two languages, the combination of a romantic statement and an advertising statement."

L. Hoek (1981) in his work entitled "La marque du titre" makes a semiotic study of "title marks in the text" and "distinguishing marks inherent in the title".

According to him, when we use a title to designate a referent, we engage in social interaction and the title becomes a speech act. It is interesting in what situation, when, for whom and according to what expectations the interlocutors use titles. For Hoek:

As a declarative statement, the title presents itself as an indecent act: the title is primarily an attachment point to which the text's recipient's attention is drawn; the relationship established between the speaker (author) and the interlocutor (reader) is traditional according to the place or place where the speech is traditionally manifested, as well as according to its content, intention and effect. In his analysis, he provides a syntactic, semantic, rhetorical, sigmatic and pragmatic description of the title.

Among the studies focused on press headlines, we studied J. Peytard (1975), for whom a page is a graphic medium in which headlines are embedded. It gives primary importance to the relationship between headlines and headlines on a newspaper page in terms of 'Headline Spacing'. "The function of headings is twofold: to provide material for 'primary meanings' (mostly conative) and to refer to the filler, the body of the article, and/or to attach information at the 'scanning' level," he says.

For P. Charaudeau (1983), the title implies "opening the way to everything that takes into account the effects of communication" and he explains the processes of textual communication in the field of pragmatics, taking into account the speech conditions surrounding the interlocutors. In this sense, news headlines belong to the discursive genre of information.

News headlines are very important; because they not only announce the news ("epiphanic" function), not only lead to the article ("guide" function), but also summarize, condense, even freeze the news to the level of "excitement". Therefore, the title will have an autonomous status; it becomes a unique text.

F. Frandsen (1990) analyzes the newspaper headline and explains that it is a part of "journalistic paratext". According to him, "it is a collection of small text units that precede or

³La Prize/Prose de Constantinople (Les Éditions de Minuit, Paris, 1965)

pass a newspaper article and are given beautiful names in journalistic jargon, such as "headline", hat, phrase".

F. Sullet-Nylander (1998) analyzes press headlines syntactically, pragmatically, and rhetorically.

In the field of linguistics, J. Ray-Debove (1978) explores the semiotic status of titles in his *Le Métalangage*.

While in the context of the work a title such as *Madame Bovary* refers to a woman, in any other context it refers to Flaubert's novel, which is the title of a work that is set in discourse and allows for saving.

In conclusion, before choosing a title of the work, several specific descriptions can be given to the specified object, because this object has the property of uniqueness that implies the description. But once the title is selected, it becomes a direct access to the referent. Take, for example, the title *The Faithful Woman*, chosen not for the meaning it conveys, but for the meaning we want to apply to the semiotic object: the work, like the proper noun, whatever attribute it may have. *i nazar*, it remains the same name.

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